

PITHIA-NRF

The integration project for an advanced plasmasphere, ionosphere and thermosphere research environment

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Abstract

The PITHIA-NRF project "Plasmasphere Ionosphere Thermosphere Integrated Research Environment and Access services: a Network of Research Facilities" aims at building a European distributed network that integrates observations from space and ground, data processing tools and prediction models to facilitate scientific research of the Plasmasphere-Ionosphere-Thermosphere system. PITHIA-NRF is designed to provide organised open access to experimental facilities and data, standardised data products, and training services. Participating organisations that operate these facilities, formed twelve nodes in eleven different countries in Europe. These nodes work for the optimisation of its observing facilities and offer trans-national access to scientists and engineers. In addition, an important part of the project is the e-Science Centre. Its structure and evolution follow a strict ontology which governs the collection of observations and models registered with the e-Science Centre. Several tens of observation and model collections have already been registered. FAIR principles and data quality management have played an important role for the registration process. Researchers agreed to implement a trans-national access project, have the possibility to discover data collections in the e-Science Centre, execute models and access the results and register new data collections for easy re-use. At the end of the project, a comprehensive collection of observations and models will have been gathered by the e-Science Centre for the benefit of efficient scientific research.

Acronyms

The following table contains the list of all acronyms used in this document.

Table 1. List of acronyms

Acronym	Definition
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure Architecture
AoLP	Angle of Linear Polarisation
API	Application Programming Interface
ASPIS	Autonomous Service for Prediction of Ionospheric Scintillations
ASTRON	Netherlands Institute for Radio Astronomy
BSPM	Belgian SWIFF Plasmasphere Model
CBK/PAS	Centrum Badań Kosmicznych PAN
CCMC	Community Coordinated Modeling Center
CDSS	Continuous Doppler Sounding System

Acronym	Definition
CHAM	CHALLENGING Mini-Satellite Payload
CIR	Corotating Interaction Region
CLI	Command Line Interface
CME	Coronal Mass Ejection
COSMIC	Constellation Observing System for Meteorology, Ionosphere and Climate
D2D	Digisonde-to-Digisonde
DC	Data Collection
DEMETER	DEMONstrating the Emerging Technology for Measuring the Earth's Radiation
DGQ	Quality of Data Generation
DLR-SO	German Aerospace Center - Institute for Solar-Terrestrial Physics
DM	Descriptive Metadata
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DoLP	Degree of Linear Polarisation
DQF	Data Quality Flag
DRQ	Quality of Data Repository
DSND	Automated data analysis procedure DSND for dynasonde measurements
DTM2020	Drag Temperature Model 2020
EC	European Commission
EGI	EGI Foundation
EGI-ACE	EGI - Advanced Computing for EOSC
e-IRG	e-Infrastructure Reflection Group
EISCAT	European Incoherent Scatter Scientific Association
EO	Earth Observation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EPB	Equatorial Plasma Bubbles
ESA	European Space Agency
eSC	e-Science Centre
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
ESPAS	Near-Earth Space Data Infrastructure for e-Science

Acronym	Definition
EUV	Extreme UltraViolet
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GOCE	Gravity field and Ocean Circulation Explorer
GRACE	Gravity Recovery and Climate Experiment
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HF	High-Frequency
HF VI	High Frequencies Variability Index
IAP	Institute of Atmospheric Physics of the Czech Academy of Science
IGRF	International Geomagnetic Reference Field
IGS	International GNSS Service
IMF	Interplanetary Magnetic Field
INGV	Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia
IONEX	IONosphere map EXchange
IPIM	IRAP Plasmasphere-Ionosphere Model
IPP	Ionospheric Pierce Point
IRI	International Reference Ionosphere
ISO	International Standards Organization
ISR	Incoherent Scatter Radar
ITP	Ionosphere, Thermosphere, and Plasmasphere
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KAIRA	Kilpisjärvi Atmospheric Imaging Receiver Array
LEO	Low Earth Orbit
LOFAR	LOw Frequency ARray
MSTID	Medium Scale Travelling Ionospheric Disturbance
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NOA	National Observatory of Athens
NPSM	Nucleon-Pair Shell Model
NRTK	Network Real Time Kinematic
O&M	Observations and Measurements
OE	Observatorio del Ebro Fundación

Acronym	Definition
PID	Persistent Identifier
PITHIA-NRF	Plasmasphere Ionosphere Thermosphere Integrated Research Environment and Access services - a Network of Research Facilities
PLIP	Polar Lights Imaging Polarimeter
PPP	Precise Point Positioning
R&D	Research and Development
RAEGE-Az	Rede Atlântica de Estações Geodinâmicas e Espaciais - Azores Association
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RELEC	Relativistic ELECtrons
RI	Research Infrastructure
RINEX	Receiver Independent Exchange
ROB	Royal Observatory of Belgium
ROT	Rate Of Chance of TEC
SAR	Synthetic-Aperture Radars
SGO	Sodankylä Geophysical Observatory
SH	Spherical Harmonic
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
SSA	Space Situational Awareness
sTEC	slant Total Electron Content
STIM	Storm Time Ionospheric Model
SWIFF	Solar Wind driven autoregression model for Ionospheric short-term Forecast
TDR	Trusted Digital Repository
TEC	Total Electron Content
TIDs	Travelling Ionospheric Disturbances
TNA	TransNational Access
TSAR	Time Series AutoRegressive
UHF	Ultra High Frequency
UI	User Interface
UPC	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya

Acronym	Definition
UPC-IonSAT	UPC - Ionospheric determination and navigation based on Satellite And Terrestrial systems
URSI	Union Radio-Scientific Internationale / International Union of Radio Science
UT3-IRAP	University Toulouse III-Paul Sabatier – Institut de Recherche en Astrophysique et Planétologie
UV	UltraViolet
VLF	Very Low Frequency
vTEC	vertical Total Electron Content
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WIONAS	Wave-like structures in the IONosphere between Athens and Sopron
XML	Extensible Markup Language
YAML	YAML Ain't Markup Language

1. Introduction

Physical processes in the Earth's ionosphere, thermosphere, and plasmasphere result in an extremely complex physical system which is the source of many scientific, operational, societal, and environmental challenges that affect the smooth and uninterrupted operation of technological systems. The affected applications are for example: (1) High-Frequency (HF) radio communication and localisation (Knipp, 2016; Witvliet, 2016), geolocation systems and associated ground- and satellite-based augmentation systems (Roy, 2013); (2) space-based communications (Dorman, 2005), communication between the Earth and ground stations and rovers at the Moon, on Mars and other planets (Barbieri, 2004; Bergeot et al., 2019); (3) communication with deep space missions (Woo, 2007); (4) low-frequency radio astronomy and Synthetic-Aperture Radars (SAR) observations (Pi, 2015). The socioeconomic impact of these effects is detailed in Vermicelli (2022).

To reach research advances in data access and analysis, in modelling developments and in the transition of models to operations, the **Plasmasphere Ionosphere Thermosphere Integrated Research Environment and Access services: a Network of Research Facilities (PITHIA-NRF) project**, funded by the Horizon 2020 programme of the European Commission, aims to build a European distributed network integrating observing facilities, data collections, data processing tools and prediction models dedicated to ionosphere, thermosphere and plasmasphere (ITP) research. PITHIA-NRF is designed to provide organised access to experimental facilities, Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable (FAIR) data, standardised data products, training and innovation services. PITHIA-NRF paves the way for new observing technologies, procedures and tools for the end-to-end transition of research models to applications tuned to meet the requirements of the

technologies concerned, linking best-in-class R&D facilities to provide seamless multi-technology services.

Europe operates a large number of world-class facilities for the observation of the Earth's Ionosphere, Thermosphere and Plasmasphere with sizes ranging from small ground-based instruments to spacecraft. However, their operation is mainly autonomous and independent using different standards, and the policies for access and exploitation are different and mainly tuned to national priorities. Due to this fragmented operation, and different access policies, researchers in Europe and worldwide cannot exploit the full potential of these important research facilities, despite the significant investments made mainly through national and regional funds.

The PITHIA-NRF integration scheme brings the research facilities, databases and models together on a European scale and renders them easily accessible to all European researchers, ensuring their optimal use and promoting cooperative development. The access to the research facilities allows users to develop their own research projects using the unique observing capabilities of the PITHIA-NRF facilities.

The facilities serve the following fundamental scientific demands:

1. Access to long-term observational data of the near-Earth space environment to build a comprehensive picture of the ITP system, and also to develop and validate models.
2. Access to validated models and their results to facilitate the training of a new generation of researchers in the basic modelling concepts, in the physics principles embedded in the empirical models.
3. Provide a platform for the development and integration of new realistic models of the upper atmosphere, the plasmasphere and the heliosphere, which are indispensable for describing, explaining and ultimately forecasting the behaviour of this complex system, and mitigating the space weather effects on vulnerable technologies.

From its inception, PITHIA-NRF has been an integral part of the global network of research infrastructures, as its foundation is based on integration principles set by EGI (a pan-European e-infrastructure), URSI, and ESA (SSA and EO Programmes) regarding data model standards and maturity scales. It relies on data collection and management standards and policies set by the EOSC, mainly provided by URSI, the IGS GNSS network (RINEX, IONEX ...) and CCMC/NASA. The adoption of specific standards is considered in the PITHIA-NRF data policy definition, which is necessary given the specificities of the upper atmosphere data sets that are a mixture of ground-based and space-borne data and contain a variety of data products extracted from models and data curation tools.

Figure 1: PITHIA-NRF landscape built through integration

In the diagram shown in Figure 1, the integrative nature of PITHIA-NRF on the landscape facilities is presented. The integration comes from the alignment and use of common standards, observation strategies, data management strategies, data formats, scientific models, and e-infrastructures. Models and data made available in the Nodes are made compatible with national e-infrastructures brought together in EGI. The integrated system provides an extended exploitation potential for users regarding observing facilities, data, application models and workflows. Delivery towards users is done via the PITHIA-NRF e-Science Centre and is promoted by EOSC. More specifically, the integration is achieved through:

- The deployment of a node, the e-Science Centre for the registration of data collections, their discovery, access and re-use.
- The development of policies for common data management and quality control.
- The creation of a space physics ontology and community metadata standard facilitating the establishment of a shared language, essential for streamlined data integration.
- The optimisation of the operation of the observing facilities operated within the PITHIA-NRF nodes and the provision of standardised access to scientists and engineers to conduct Research and Development projects.

The following sections provide details about the implementation of integrated activities and the outlook for the sustainability of the PITHIA-NRF Research Infrastructure on a long-term perspective.

2. The network of research facilities

The Network of Research Facilities consists of 12 nodes that provide access to key observing and data processing infrastructures for the investigation and modelling of physical processes acting in the Earth’s upper atmosphere. Access to PITHIA-NRF nodes is provided to selected users after the successful evaluation of their Transnational access (TNA) research proposals. The access can be awarded either for hands-on projects or for remote implementation. For both cases, the choices that are available to the applicants are summarised in Figure 2.

Figure 2: PITHIA-NRF TNA choices

2.1 Research priorities in PITHIA-NRF nodes

Table 2 provides a short description of the topic of research specialisation of each node and the indicative research topics for project implementation by external research users.

Table 2. Nodes research specialisation

PITHIA-NRF nodes	Indicative research topics for implementation by scientific users
NOA node: HF VI experiments and ionospheric models <i>Operated by NOA, Athens (Palaia Penteli), Greece</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ionospheric modelling for nowcasting and forecasting purposes: Modelling formulation of ionospheric storm effects at middle latitudes driven by solar wind input; Data - driven ionospheric specification models, using different training data sets and/or deep-learning techniques; Ensemble modelling for ionospheric predictions using heliospheric forecasting models;

PITHIA-NRF nodes	Indicative research topics for implementation by scientific users
	<p>Reconstruction of electron density profile by ingesting ground and space-based observations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Validation of ionospheric specification models compatible with international practices - Ionospheric data control: development of higher-level data-products based on ionospheric autoscaled data filtering algorithms - Ionospheric irregularities and travelling ionospheric disturbances (TIDs): identification and propagation patterns for TIDs; bottomside and topside ionosphere interactions; identification of post-seismic effects in the ionosphere - Digisonde experiments: vertical soundings and joint experiments/special campaigns with bistatic HF sounders' operations.
<p>EISCAT node: Incoherent scatter radar (ISR) and other high power large aperture radar experiments, Dynasonde data <i>Operated by EISCAT, Kiruna, Sweden</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Auroral and polar cap electrodynamics - Space environment - atmosphere coupling at the statistical southern edges of the polar vortex and the auroral oval - Thermosphere-ionosphere coupling - ISR/HF experiments - ISR WorldDay collaboration - Meteoroids, dust particles and near-Earth objects - Ionospheric 3D imaging - Dynasonde database (DSND/NeXtYZ parameters, ionospheric irregularities)
<p>LOFAR node: low-frequency radio observations <i>Operated by ASTRON, The Netherlands</i></p>	<p>Ionospheric scintillation at low radio frequencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assessment of any association with scintillation seen by GNSS - Assessment of any association with large-scale structures (e.g., TIDs) detected and modelled by other instruments.
<p>CBK/PAS node: multi-instrument diagnostics of plasma structures <i>Operated by CBK/PAS, Warsaw, Poland</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quantification of the impact of magnetosphere–ionosphere coupling on auroral region boundary layers behaviour using satellite in situ measurements from DEMETER, RELEC, COSMIC, as well as measurements from ground-based infrastructures - Implementation of novel techniques based on LOFAR diagnostics for determining the characteristics of small and middle scales ionospheric irregularities

PITHIA-NRF nodes	Indicative research topics for implementation by scientific users
<p>SGO node: High latitude ionosphere physics experiments</p> <p><i>Operated by the Sodankyla Geophysical Observatory, Finland</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Auroral electrodynamics using entire Finnish Pulsation Magnetometer network, comparison to visual auroral oval and exploitation of IL and IU indices - Electron precipitation from KAIRA, comparison to model results - Ionospheric D region cosmic noise absorption using riometer network and KAIRA observations
<p>UT3 IRAP node: Plasmasphere-Ionosphere Thermosphere modelling</p> <p><i>Operated by UT3-IRAP, Toulouse, France</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Validation of the IRAP Plasmasphere-Ionosphere Model (IPIM) results especially during solar eclipses, solar flares, CIRs or CMEs, using data from ionospheric stations, SuperDARN radars and GNSS satellites signals; - Quantification of Joule heating and energetic particle precipitation heating at auroral latitudes through IPIM modelling fed with realistic inputs such as SuperDARN convection, satellites particle precipitation; - Assessment of the thermosphere characteristics during perturbed periods (CIRs, CMEs) and their effect on the IPIM ionosphere modelling at high and middle latitudes. Comparison with ionospheric observations (ionosondes, EISCAT radars...).
<p>ROB GNSS node: GNSS hardware calibration and data processing facility</p> <p><i>Operated by the ROB GNSS group, Brussels, Belgium</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adaptation of the ROB-IONO software process global data. - Post-processing and nowcasting products on vTEC and sTEC at ionospheric pierce points. - Test for Galileo inclusions in the processing - Multi-GNSS comparison to test interoperability of the different systems. - GNSS hardware delay estimation
<p>UPC IonSAT node: Precise GNSS modelling for new scientific and technical applications.</p> <p><i>Operated by UPC IonSAT group, Barcelona, Spain</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Global Tomographic modelling of the ionosphere computed with multifrequency GNSS phase-carrier observations. - Electron density profiles derived from LEO based GNSS radio-occultation measurements. - GNSS-Ionosphere Measurement of Solar Extreme UltraViolet (EUV) variation during solar flares

PITHIA-NRF nodes	Indicative research topics for implementation by scientific users
<p>OE node: HF Digisonde-to-Digisonde (D2D) experiments <i>Operated by OE, Roquetes, Spain</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - HF D2D experiments to improve ionospheric specification in west Europe. - Identification and specification of Large Scale Travelling Ionospheric Disturbances. - Identification and specification of Plasma Depletions. - Solar flare absorption effects on radio signals.
<p>IAP node: Ionosphere-lower atmosphere coupling, <i>Operated by IAP, Prague, Czech Republic</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Analysis of wave coupling processes and consequences in the whole atmosphere and ionosphere using CDSSs and European Digisonde network measurements - Validation of medium scale TIDs detection techniques - Ionosphere/gravity wave climatology - Troposphere – upper atmosphere – solar wind coupling studies exploiting atmospheric electricity, ionosphere and solar wind data
<p>INGV node: ionospheric irregularities: specification, modelling and mitigation <i>Operated by INGV, Rome, Italy</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ionospheric scintillations: Monitoring, modelling and forecasting - Mitigation algorithms/techniques for HF communications (Ray tracing) and for ionospheric scintillations on high accuracy positioning (PPP, NRTK) and Synthetic Aperture Radar Imaging; - Ionospheric correction for augmentation systems in challenging areas (high and low latitudes)
<p>DLR-SO node: Space weather impact in the ionosphere and plasmasphere and mitigation of the effects <i>Operated by DLR, Neustrelitz, Germany</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Solar flare monitoring and analysis of the ionospheric response. - Impact analysis for HF communication and GNSS performances by combination with GNSS measurements (TEC, TEC rates) - Spectral analyses to study radiation impacts on the lower ionosphere - Research and analysis of D-Layer ionosphere disturbances from below (Gravity waves, Earthquakes, Hurricanes, radiation sources) - Analysis of ionospheric response during Solar Eclipse events - Cross correlation with external data sets from users (e.g. in the domain of GNSS-positioning or communication) to check the vulnerability of their systems to solar flare events

PITHIA-NRF nodes	Indicative research topics for implementation by scientific users
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Specification of topside ionosphere and plasmasphere electron density using NPSM

Once a proposal is positively evaluated and accepted for implementation in a PITHIA-NRF node, the TransNational Access (TNA) project is implemented. PITHIA-NRF TNA programme released five open calls since the start of PITHIA-NRF Horizon 2020 project. These calls are detailed in the project web site, regarding the commitments from the side of the project and the side of the applicants and the evaluation criteria. With the help of PITHIA-NRF TNA programme, more than twenty projects are finished or are still under implementation in the individual nodes.

2.2 TNA services and optimisation of observing strategies

The operation of PITHIA-NRF nodes as a network of research facilities is expected to gain scientific usefulness through the optimisation of observing strategies. The optimisation aims to provide a framework for the operators and managers of the PITHIA-NRF facilities to interact, exchange their expertise, discuss new ideas and concepts, share the outcomes of the TNA projects, and provide education and critical insight to users. In addition, it is expected to develop interfaces with innovation actions, reaching out to the engineering community (including SMEs), and to the space agencies who have specific requirements for technology readiness and standardisation in instrumentation and software. In this framework, specific activities have already been carried out in PITHIA-NRF nodes to promote the networking concept and the design of new scientific services based on the needs expressed by the scientific/engineering community and by the space industry. Below we list some implemented TNA projects that are representative of the success of the TNA program:

- Travelling Ionospheric Disturbances (TIDs) detection software codes and relevant data collections, provided by the NOA node, have been exploited by the WIONAS TNA project to identify wave structures propagating within the ionosphere above the South-East European region. Ionosonde measurements, including ionograms and Digisonde-to-Digisonde measurements between Athens and Sopron Digisonde stations - were analysed. The geographical location of the two stations provides a unique opportunity to study wave-like ionospheric anomalies in the South-East European region. Based on the data availability from the two Digisonde stations, some recent geomagnetic storms and lower atmosphere dynamic events were selected for further study. TID results obtained from Digisonde measurements, and from the HF Interferometry method and from the GNSS gradient method, were analysed to extract conclusions regarding the triggering source of the observed TIDs.
- Portuguese regional ionosphere maps – PRIMA. In this TNA the sTEC calibration of the multi-frequency GNSS measurements of the RAEGE-Az (Rede Atlântica de Estações Geodinâmicas e Espaciais - Azores Association, <https://raege-az.pt/en/>) GNSS network was performed supported on the UPC-IonSAT Global Ionospheric Maps.

- The TNA Magneto-ionospheric modelling through Faraday rotation in Pulsar data, made possible the improvement of the correction of Earth ionosphere Faraday rotation effect in LOFAR measurements. At the same time the performance of three models of the ionosphere using observations of the source PSR~J0332+5434 taken with the LOw Frequency ARray (LOFAR), were compared.
- The implementation of the methodologies developed using multi-instrument data, and establishing validation procedures fundamentally using information between the different observation systems, made possible to investigate the influences and dependences of ionospheric plasma depletions to geomagnetic storms, and the study of modelling methods using ionosonde data in combination with other measurement techniques. The latter was used to analyse localised processes that are produced by the interaction between the solar wind and magnetospheric forcing and the ionosphere, specifically the characterisation of localised plasma depletions. The work combined ionosonde, satellite UV imaging, GNSS-ROTI, and all-sky imaging data to characterise the ionospheric plasma depletion observed at latitudes as high as in Spain during the geomagnetic storm of 27 February 2014, and interrelated its variations in space and time with the different multi-instrument data.
- The ionospheric response to Space Hurricane has been analysed for four case events by combining observations of GNSS and Ionosonde showing that Space Hurricane can cause travelling Ionospheric disturbance at high latitudes and that might impact the behaviour of the ionosphere at mid-latitudes
- A group of researchers at the Royal Belgian Institute for Space Aeronomy (BIRA-IASB) developed an imaging polarimeter called PLIP (Polar Lights Imaging Polarimeter). It measures the linear polarisation (Degree of Linear Polarisation (DoLP) and the Angle of Linear Polarisation (AoLP)) of the three main auroral emissions (green, red and blue) on a large field of view on the sky. Thanks to the TNA of PITHIA-NRF, they obtained 8 hours of observations with EISCAT during a 10-day observation campaign with PLIP located at the Skibotn Observatory in Norway in November 2022. They found an interesting case: a strong decrease of DoLP and a clear rotation of AoLP occurs during the main phase of a geomagnetic storm clearly identified by ground-based magnetometer data from Tromsø and UHF radar data from EISCAT. These observations tend to favour scattering by electrons (possibly in the geomagnetic currents) as the source of polarisation.
- The TNA activity *Feasibility study of data-driven Autonomous Service for Prediction of Ionospheric Scintillations (ASPIS)* between the DLR-SO node and the Institute of Experimental Physics at the Slovak Academy of Sciences in Košice, Slovakia was dedicated to study the feasibility of developing a data-driven service autonomously providing an assessment of ionospheric scintillation in a specific time ahead, based on available solar, space weather, geomagnetic, ionospheric, and thermospheric data for a particular location. The objectives within the TNA, which also included a one-week workshop at DLR-SO, were to become familiar with data of ionospheric scintillation (S_4 , $\sigma\phi$, ROTI) and other ionospheric parameters provided by DLR-SO, to incorporate these data into an existing data-driven approach, to investigate the performance of ASPIS in comparison with other current prediction models of ionospheric parameters and to compile user needs and requirements for ionospheric prediction service for future demonstration purposes and for potential operation purposes.

3. PITHIA Metadata Schema and Ontology

PITHIA metadata are registered in the PITHIA e-Science Centre (see section 4) by data providers. Descriptions of Resources are written as Extensible Markup Language (XML) documents that comply with three governing requirements:

- The PITHIA *Schema*, that controls organisation of the registration documents:
 - *The Schema* is based on the International Standards Organization (ISO) 19100 series of standards for geographic information, particularly 19156:2011 “Observations and Measurements” (O&M) standard;
 - ISO 19156:2011 was adapted and extended for the space physics domain by the data model team of ESPAS (Near-Earth Space Data Infrastructure for e-Science) European Commission FP7 project, during its 2014-2017 period of performance (Belehaki et al., 2016);
 - The ESPAS Schema has been adapted, simplified, and extended for PITHIA-NRF to meet specific project requirements.
- The PITHIA *Ontology*, that controls the standard vocabulary of terms specific to the domain of space physics:
 - The Ontology is based on the original ESPAS Ontology design (Galkin & Behlaki, 2017), with extensions specific to PITHIA-NRF datasets and models.
- The XML *Syntax*, that controls formatting of registration documents per World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) definitions.

Registration of new metadata in PITHIA-NRF is described in more detail in section 4.1.

3.1 PITHIA Schema

The ISO 19156:2011 O&M standard provides the following core properties for an observation (or a computational model that predicts an observation):

- Feature of Interest: a real-world object that carries the property which is observed or modelled to produce a Data Collection, such as the Earth’s ionosphere;
- Observed Property: description of a physical Phenomenon obtained by means of observation or modelling that generates an estimate of its Measurand value;
 - Phenomenon is a physically observable entity; the top-level Phenomenon categories are Particle, Field, and Wave;
 - Measurand is the quantitative or qualitative attribute of the Phenomenon to be evaluated, such as velocity, flux, density, etc.
- Result: data generated by the act of observation or modelling;
- Procedure: a sequence of Acquisitions and Computations that lead to a Result.

The ESPAS Schema provides a significant extension to the ISO O&M standard needed to describe space physics observations in detail, and particularly to allow each Observation result to be registered with its individual Phenomenon Time, Spatial Extent, and particular subsets of Procedure as well as Observed Properties that were used during the Observation.

The PITHIA Schema underwent a significant simplification of the ESPAS design. To improve its scalability to collections of multi-million observations (that would each have required an individual metadata registration document), the PITHIA Schema introduced a new concept of Data Collection, that captures the exhaustive set of possible Procedures' Acquisition and Computation components, with all possible Observed Properties, and all Platforms that host the registered sensor Instruments. Thus, the PITHIA Schema omits the specifics of each individual Observation act, including their Phenomenon Time, Spatial Extent, and used components of Procedure. This simplification has delegated all functionality of data search by coincidence or conjunction to the original data providers, who remain responsible for the service functions that respond to incoming queries for temporal and spatial availability of data in the Data Collections. Instead, the PITHIA Schema adds a new Resource Catalogue for registration of Data Collection subsets of interest in a specific underlying physical event, investigation, or academic publication. The Catalogue data subsets are provided with particular Phenomenon Time and Spatial Extent descriptions, as well as a standard Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to meet FAIR requirements.

3.2 PITHIA Ontology

Most of the PITHIA Ontology definitions are the original RDF (Resource Description Framework) documents developed by the ESPAS ontology team and available publicly at <https://ontology.espas-fp7.eu/vocabs>. As the PITHIA data registration proceeds, new terms and definitions are added to the Ontology that were not required previously. The most active areas of such extensions are Computation Type, Phenomenon, and Dimensionality vocabularies to describe data collections generated by models and sensors that were not available in ESPAS.

The Space Physics Ontology option in the e-Science Centre offers dynamic browsing of the ontology, allowing Scientific Users to find definitions for terms in the ontology, and understand how the various terms relate to each other. This is a very important function as all the registered metadata relate to each other based on ontology terms.

4. The e-Science Centre

In addition to the 12 nodes that provide access to research infrastructures, a central node, the e-Science Centre (eSC) also operates in PITHIA-NRF, for registration, access and re-use of Data Collections and Catalogues. *Data collections* can be either datasets or results from scientific models, offered by providers inside or even outside PITHIA. On the other hand, *Catalogues* are smaller sets of data that describe a certain event related to, for example, a publication. Data Collections can be live and changing/growing constantly. On the other hand, Catalogues refer to fixed sets of data that can also be assigned a DOI and referenced in scientific publications to support reproducibility.

eSC services have been defined in five different categories, as illustrated in Figure 3. At the bottom of the figure are the various Security Services, such as authentication, authorisation, data protection and privacy management. These services are essential and required, and provide the basis for the other, higher-level services. On top of the Security Services, the e-

Science Centre provides the User Management Services. While access to some (most) material and resources is open in the PITHIA e-Science Centre, there is still a need for authentication and authorisation of at least some user groups (e.g. Data Collection owners, e-Science Centre administrators, etc.). Therefore, User Account Management still remains a necessary service to enable the creation and management of user accounts.

Figure 3: PITHIA e-Science Services

PITHIA e-Science Centre users are presented with three major categories of services: Information and Community Services, e-Learning Services, and Scientific Services. Information and Community Services provide mainly static information about the community in the form of news items or blogs, but this service category also incorporates more dynamic services that enable networking and collaboration between scientists or even with the general public. E-Learning Services provide access to learning and research material in an organised and systematic way. The PITHIA e-Science Centre users are able to search for learning and research material based on an associated ontology, and could design and create learning graphs and paths that make them better understand and follow the various scientific and technical concepts associated with the resources of the e-Science Centre.

Finally, Scientific Services allow users to access e-Science Centre resources, namely Data Collections and Catalogues. Such resources are published by resource owners (i.e. Data Collection and Catalogue owners) using a rich set of metadata, and made available for scientific users to search, find and utilise them based on their scientific goals and requirements. Users will also get access to a general helpdesk and ticketing system <https://ggus.eu/>, which is especially important if questions arise when accessing Data Collections or executing Models.

The eSC is under constant development, and the roadmap has been set for adding new features and functionalities. At the moment of writing this article, the eSC offers three main functionalities. Its home page is shown in Figure 4.

The three main categories of functionalities are:

1. The Search & Browse category is accessible to all Scientific Users without the requirement to log in and allows any user to:

- Search for Data Collections by specifying a selection of ontology terms, or by simple freetext search
- Browse all registered Data Collections.
- Browse all registered Catalogues.
- Browse all registered Metadata related to the twelve-step registration process.

2. The Space Physics Ontology category that allows any user to:

- Search for terms and their definitions
- Access the Space Physics Ontology Guide

3. The Data Registration category that allows:

- Any user to access and download the detailed Data Resource Registration Guide.
- Authenticated users (after logging in) to register new Data Collections through associated XML-based metadata.
- Authenticated users to modify or delete existing Data Collections.

Additionally, the XML schemas, which may be of interest to advanced users, are also available in this category after authentication.

Figure 4: e-Science Centre Home Page

The first official prototype was released (May 2023) with the functionalities detailed in this document. The next large milestone is coming in March 2024 with the release of the second prototype. This second prototype will provide full user management capabilities and the implementation of further Data Collection execution methods. Additionally, it is expected that most Data Collections will be accessible via one or more interaction methods (see section 4.2). During the final year of the project the implementation of advanced services (workflow capabilities and machine learning algorithms) will be investigated and implemented as appropriate.

4.1 Registration and Management

Registration of new PITHIA metadata is accomplished by submitting XML documents to the eSC portal <https://esc.pithia.eu/>, where all documents are validated against the governing requirements of the PITHIA *Schema*, PITHIA *Ontology*, and XML *Syntax*.

As it was explained earlier, to access the hidden features (Data Collection and Catalogue **registration, management and deletion** functionalities) of the e-Science Centre (<https://esc.pithia.eu/>) user **login** is required. The additional functionalities available to authorised users are shown in Figure 5.

Data Registration

Figure 5: Data Registration features in PITHIA eSC

The Data Registration group of functionalities focuses mainly on how Organisations and their Members can register metadata. Any member of an organisation has the authority to register, update and delete metadata under the Register & Manage Metadata option. They can register both Data Collections and Catalogues, modify earlier registrations or delete unnecessary ones. Additionally, the Metadata Registration Guide is a document that explains the structure of the Metadata and how Organisations should create and register them in compliance with the PITHIA schema. Finally, the Metadata Models option presents all the schemas that each registration item is validated against before it can be registered.

When an organisation member selects the Register & Manage Metadata option, the eSC offers two options:

- Data Collection-related Metadata, where they can manage registrations related to the twelve-steps registration process.
- Catalogue-related Metadata, where they can manage registration related to the three Catalogue categories.

Data Collection – related metadata are registered following the sequence of twelve steps as shown in Figure 6. All PITHIA-NRF data resources are registered with the e-Science Centre using the International Standards Organisation guidelines for Observations and Measurements (ISO 19156:2011). PITHIA-NRF leverages metadata designs for space physics data registration developed by the ESPAS consortium (Belehaki et al., 2016) in 2012-2015. At the time of the PITHIA-NRF project performance, the governing ISO standards prescribe using XML as the physical format. Therefore, all PITHIA data registrations are done using XML as the metadata format.

To facilitate the registration process, document templates are provided for each step. Editing replaces the example content with resource-specific information. Each template is pre-structured according to the PITHIA metadata model. Such a template-based approach is making the registration process significantly easier, with less likelihood of errors. However, to make the process fully robust, the e-Science Centre always goes through a set of comprehensive checks of every uploaded document. First, it checks the XML syntax for any formal errors. Second, it assures that all XML documents are in-line with the defined XML schemas and the PITHIA ontology. Finally, it guarantees that all other XML documents that are referred to from the currently uploaded one do exist. In case of any errors eSC notifies the user pointing to the origin of the problem. With this rigorous process, errors (except semantic errors that refer to the scientific content or logic) can be eliminated.

Figure 6: Twelve steps of PITHIA data resource registration. Different colours are used to indicate the complexity of the definitions; blue ovals are harder to define. OP is *Observed Property* information commonly used for content-aware searches.

Data resource registration is organised using the concept of the Metadata Model and of the Domain Ontology:

- Metadata Model: ISO-controlled organisation of the metadata components and their relationships in a generic, science-neutral manner;
- Domain Ontology: a vocabulary of physical concepts pertaining to a particular domain of science; usually structured and provided with wider-narrower relationships.

The PITHIA Space Physics Ontology for content-aware data collection registration at PITHIA e-Science Centre is detailed in the guide available in the e-Science Centre by Galkin (2023).

Catalogues are listings of events or investigations assembled to aid users in locating data of interest. Each Catalogue entry has distinct begin and end times and an optional DOI to the Data Subset in a permanent storage. Catalogues are not part of the standard Data Collection registration. The catalogues are managed separately, based on the Data Collections in PITHIA eScience Centre. There are three types of components of each Catalogue:

1. Top-level Catalogue Category (e.g., Catalog_VolcanoEruption)

a. The Catalogue Category is ontology-controlled

2. Individual entries of the Catalogue describing each specific event or investigation (e.g. HungaTonga_2022-01-15)

a. Each entry has a description and PhenomenonTime

b. Each entry is linked to the Catalogue Category document

3. Data Subset items (e.g. Manually Scaled Ionograms)

a. Each Data Subset refers to a Data Collection

b. Each Data Subset includes <resultTime> to define intervals of time that the subset spans

c. Optionally, the data provider may specify a DOI for the persistent storage of the Data Subset - DOI generation is directly supported by the eSC, but it can also be generated externally

4.2 Data Collection Interaction Methods

One of the most important aspects of the eSC is to provide methods to enable interaction with models and datasets (Data Collections). Such interactions will enable scientists to execute a model on-demand, or retrieve, visualise and manipulate data from a dataset or an underlying database. As this is the ultimate aim of the eSC, it is important that the system caters for multiple options and requirements.

In general, the implementation of each interaction method should be simple for the resource provider and as automated as possible. Four different interaction methods are supported in

the eSC. Each Data Collection (DC) provider can decide which method they implement. It is essential to provide at least one interaction method, otherwise users cannot access the DC. For further flexibility, implementing multiple interaction methods is also supported.

The currently planned interaction methods in the eSC are summarised below. The first two of these methods have already been implemented and integrated into the eSC. The last two methods are currently under investigation and prototyping.

1. Get a link once the Data Collection is found

This method is fully implemented and a natural part of the Data Collection registration process. In this method, the Data Collection provider registers a link to the Data Collection in the “linkage” field of the DC’s XML registration file. When a user finds a DC as a result of search or browse, the eSC displays this link based on the XML registration document. Once clicking on the link, the user is redirected to an external site/repository managed by the PITHIA partners in order to access and interact with the DC.

The major advantage of this method is its simplicity. The provider does not have to do anything extra on top of the actual registration. However, the method also comes with shortcomings. As the link takes the user outside the eSC, all functionalities are reduced to the capabilities of the provider’s services. While this method allows users to find and discover Data Collections from the single entry point of the eSC, it does not provide further integration beyond this.

2. Execute Model within the e-Science Centre via API

In this method the provider has to implement (if not already available) an API (ideally, following the OpenAPI standard <https://www.openapis.org/>) to execute a model or query/retrieve dataset. Next, a machine readable YAML or JSON specification of this API needs to be created (or preferably, generated automatically). Finally, this API specification needs to be registered in the eSC by simply providing a link to it. Using this specification, the e-Science Centre automatically generates a graphical user interface to interact with the Data Collection. This method is also fully implemented in the eSC.

This method provides much closer integration with the eSC than the first one. When a user interacts with the Data Collection, this is happening from inside the eSC. The look and feel is the same for every application and as such it is easier for the users to get accustomed to it. On the negative side, the task of DC providers is significantly bigger. They need to assure that the Data Collection is accessible via a suitable API and they have to provide a formal specification of it (although, there are several software tools that automate this process). This may require significant development effort on the producer side, especially in case of older legacy Data Collections.

3. Dynamically deploy Data Collection (Model) in the Cloud

This method is not implemented yet and only a preliminary specification and a proof of concept exist regarding its realisation (Pierantoni, Kiss & Bolotov et.al., 2022). The core of the idea is to take a containerised version of the Data Collection and deploy it dynamically on-demand in cloud computing resources (Kiss, Kacsuk & Kovacs et al., 2019). This scenario would require the Data Collection provider to containerise the application and then upload it to a suitable

container repository (e.g. DockerHub¹). After this, the provider also needs to describe the Data Collection with a YAML²-based description file (Pierantoni, Kiss & Terstyanszky et al. 2020). When a user selects the DC, it gets deployed in the cloud and a copy of it is executed specifically for the user. Once it is not required anymore (e.g. execution terminates or the user decides to delete the service), it gets destroyed. The method is specifically suitable for models that can be deployed as a set of microservices and then executed.

The advantage of the method is its flexible execution in the cloud. Using cloud resources and only utilising these when necessary is scalable and cost effective. On the negative side, this approach requires the most expertise and effort from the provider.

By interfacing the e-Science Centre and the dynamic deployer module with EGI, we can ensure deployability into 30 national/regional OpenStack clouds which are federated in the EGI Cloud Compute service. This network can give PITHIA and its users the possibility to select the national cloud resources for each user, lowering/eliminating the need for cross-national compute consumption.

4. Download and install Data Collection on local computer

This method also has not been implemented yet while it requires only a minor effort. The idea is to package and make the Data Collection (typically a model) available for download and installation by the provider. The download happens through the eSC. Once users find the model via browse or search, they can download and install it in the local environment.

The advantage of this method is its simplicity for all parties. However, on the negative side, it is only suitable for small models that are executable on the user's local machine.

In the next section a more detailed description of the second method is provided. As described it has already been implemented and provides a higher level of integration as compared to the first method.

4.3 Registration of PITHIA models via API

The objective behind this interaction method is to provide Scientific Users with a Graphical User Interface (GUI) that gives homogeneous access to all Data Collections that have implemented an API. Most Data Collections have their custom GUI, which Scientific Users must learn before interacting with the Data Collection. There are also Data Collections without a GUI for access. These may come with a Command Line Interface (CLI), which Scientific Users must get access to and learn how to use. When an organisation registers a Data Collection by also providing an API, it provides the Scientific Users two benefits. When a Scientific User uses the API as an interaction method:

- The eSC dynamically generates a GUI specifically dedicated to that Data Collection. For all Data Collections, the look and feel will be similar in the eSC, the only difference between the various Data Collections being that they will offer different options for available actions.

¹ DockerHub - <https://hub.docker.com/>

² YAML - <https://yaml.org/>

- The eSC will not redirect the user to any external source but will handle the communication with the Data Collection itself, and the Scientific User will stay in the eSC.

Additionally, for those Data Collections that do not offer a GUI and are available only through CLIs, it is much simpler for the providers to create an API than to build a GUI, as they relieve themselves from creating and maintaining the custom views of the GUI.

The tool that the eSC uses to produce the automatically generated GUI is Swagger UI³. The source code of Swagger UI has been customised and integrated into the eSC in a dedicated Django Application that reads the API specification, creates the interface, and handles the communication with the Data Collection's API. Figure 7 below presents the two steps a Scientific User has to take to interact with an API. On the left hand side, the Scientific Users must select one of the search or browse options of the eSC and find the Data Collection they want to interact with. Suppose the Data Collection offers an API, the Scientific User can click the link - Open API Interface in new tab - and the eSC will dynamically generate an interface, as illustrated in the right hand side of Figure 10. Following this, the Scientific Users can perform any of the available actions and conduct their scientific research by communicating with the Data Collection's API. A few examples when accessing and executing models from the eSC utilising its API are presented below.

Figure 7: Interacting with Data Collections through an API

Several models are registered in the eSC using API as an interaction method. Some examples are presented below:

Drag Temperature Model - DTM2020

The Drag Temperature Model 2020 (DTM2020; Bruinsma and Boniface, 2021) is a semi-empirical model of the thermosphere. Its main application is in orbit determination and prediction. It provides point-wise predictions of total mass density (in g/cm³), temperature (K), and partial densities of the main constituents (O₂, N₂, O, He in g/cm³). The solar driver is F10.7 and the geomagnetic driver of the model is Kp (Matzka et al, 2021). The backbone of the data used to fit the model coefficients are the high-resolution and precision accelerometer-inferred densities of the GOCE, CHAMP and GRACE missions.

³ Swagger UI - <https://swagger.io/tools/swagger-ui/>

Figures 8-9 display the dynamically generated DTM2020 interface through the eSC. The Data Collection offers three actions: execute the model, create plots and download fall results, as shown in Figure 8. The generation of a plot from an earlier execution is demonstrated in Figure 9 where the id of the execution and the selected variable to be plotted are provided.

Figure 8: Interacting with DTM2020 through its API - available actions

Figure 9: Specifying parameters of a plot in DTM2020

BSPM: 3D-Kinetic plasmasphere model

The BSPM (Belgian SWIFF Plasmasphere Model) is a 3D-Kinetic semiempirical model of the plasmasphere developed by the Solar Wind Division of the Royal Belgian Institute for Space Aeronomy (Pierrard et al., 2021 for the last version). Based on physical mechanisms for the plasmopause formation and trajectories of particles trapped in the Earth's magnetic field, it

provides the number density and the temperature of the electrons and protons inside and outside the plasmasphere, as well as the position of the plasmopause, as a function of the geomagnetic activity driven by the Kp index. During geomagnetic storms, the plasmasphere is eroded and structures like plasma plumes and channels can appear (Pierrard and Stegen, 2008). During quiet times, the ionosphere refills the plasmasphere. The model is coupled to the International Reference Ionosphere (IRI) model (<http://irimodel.org/>) used to determine the number density and temperatures of the particles between 60 and 700 km of altitude (Pierrard and Voiculescu, 2011). The values at 700 km are used as boundary conditions to provide the density and temperatures up to 10 Earth radii inside and outside the plasmasphere. The density in the plasma trough region has recently been improved using observations of Van Allen Probes (Botek et al., 2021). The model is running in a near-real-time basis by the name of 'SPM' at the Space Situational Awareness site (<https://swe.ssa.esa.int/bira-swiff-federated/>) of ESA (European Space Agency) using a previous IDL-Fortran version that evaluates the electron density and temperature without the ionosphere coupling, and providing animations of the equatorial and meridian plasmasphere dynamics for all the archived dates since 2017.

A PYTHON-Fortran version BSPM by the name of 'BPIM' is available in the frame of the ESA Virtual Space Weather Modeling Centre (<https://swe.ssa.esa.int/kul-cmpa-federated/>) for on-demand executions. In the present implementation at the PITHIA eSC, a more updated version of the PYTHON-Fortran implementation is available providing the electron density of the plasmasphere, the ionosphere coupling as well as the electron density beyond the plasmopause, i.e., the plasma trough for the requested day, as illustrated in Figure 10. Output of the model consists of text files and figures for every hour of a simulated day.

The screenshot shows the PITHIA-NRF e-Science Centre website. The header includes the logo, navigation links (HOME, SEARCH & BROWSE, ADMIN), and a Logout button. Below the header, there is a breadcrumb trail: Home / Present. The main content area features a section titled "Interact with Data Collection via API" for the "BSPM: 3D-Kinetic plasmasphere model". Below this, the "BSPM API: 3D-Kinetic plasmasphere model" is detailed with a URL and a description: "The BSPM is a 3D-Kinetic semiempirical model of the plasmasphere developed by the Solar Wind Division of the Royal Belgian Institute for Space Aeronomy." A search bar is present with the placeholder text "Start typing to filter sections...". Below the search bar, there are five expandable sections, each with a blue header and a dropdown arrow:

- Execute** (Run/Returns the status of execution id: year-month-day)
 - Execute the BSPM by passing the date.
- Retrieve Executions** (Returns a list of executions completed by the user)
 - Retrieve a list of user executions.
- Plot** (Returns the plot image)
 - Plot the output image by passing the execution id and hour.
- Download** (Returns the ZIP file of all outputs, including .png and .csv files)
 - Download all the outputs by passing the execution id.

Figure 10: Example of result of the BSPM model: electron number density in the plasmasphere (orange region) coupled with the ionosphere (red region), in the plasma trough (blue region) and position of the plasmapause (black circles) in the equatorial plane (left panel) and in the meridian plane (right panes) on 7 May 1994 6h UT. Plume occurrence is due to the high values of the Bartels geomagnetic index Kp which is shown at the top panel.

Height of F2 peak in quiet conditions Model (hmF2_qModel)

The hmF2_qModel (Altadill et al., 2013) model calculates and predicts the ionospheric electron density peak height of the F2 region, hmF2, in quiet conditions. The model has been generated using monthly average electron density profiles from digisonde stations distributed worldwide for a large time interval. The hmF2 have been analysed to obtain the quiet-time behaviour and have been analytically modelled by spherical harmonic analysis (SH) technique. The coefficients of the SH model of hmF2 are bound to the solar activity. The smoothed sunspot number and IGRF coefficients are used as inputs and it returns as output the F peak value in km. The model provides a calculation of the hmF2 in quiet conditions anywhere in the range of latitudes between of 70N and 70S and at any time until December 2029, and the model is able to forecast the hmF2 using the predicted smoothed sunspot number and the newest IGRF coefficients.

Time series file	Returns a csv file for the monthly averages of the Fpeak model at different hours.	^
Hmf2 Time Series File Response		v
Time series plot	Returns a plot for the monthly averages of the Fpeak model at different hours.	^
Hmf2 Time Series Plot		v
Heatmap snapshot file	Returns a csv file for different latitudes and longitudes of the monthly averaged Fpeak model at an hour for a certain spatial time window.	^
Hmf2 Map File		v
Heatmap snapshot	Returns a heatmap of the monthly averaged Fpeak model at an hour for a certain spatial time window.	^
Hmf2 Map		v
Heatmap daily animation	Returns an hourly animation of the monthly averaged Fpeak model for a certain spatial time window. The execution may take a while 🕒. You can go for a coffee if you want ☕.	^
Hmf2 Map Gif		v

Run /hmf2_map/ Clear

Responses

Details

Figure 11: Example of results of hmF2_qModel, the map shows the hmF2 over Europe in quiet conditions at 23 UT of December 2020.

F-Layer Thickness (B0) and shape (B1) quiet model (B0B1_qModel)

The B0B1_qModel (Altadill et al. 2009) calculates and predicts the thickness B0 (km) and shape B1 (dimensionless) parameters of the F layer under quiet conditions on the basis of climatological models. This empirical model has been constructed by using long time series obtained from different world-wide-distributed ionosonde stations. B0B1_qmodel estimates analytically the above parameters by SH bounded to the smoothed sunspot number and the IGRF coefficients at any location distributed along the used range of latitudes (70N–70S). Model parameters can be computed either to estimate B0 and B1 under quiet conditions or to perform predictions until December 2029 using the predicted smoothed sunspot number and the newest IGRF coefficients.

Figure 12: Example of results of B0B1_qModel, the map shows the B0 parameter over Europe in quiet conditions at 23 UT of December 2020.

Equatorial plasma Bubbles detection tool (EPB_detectionTool)

The Equatorial Plasma Bubbles (EPB) detection tool (Blanch et al. 2018) is a method to identify the occurrence and its main observables (duration, depth of the depletion and the total disturbance) with data gathered from receivers of Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS). This method adapts a previously existing technique to detect Medium Scale Travelling Ionospheric Disturbance (MSTIDs), which focuses on the second derivative of the total electron content (TEC) estimated from GNSS signals. The tool is available for a set of 52 IGS stations from 2009 to the day before yesterday. Stations have been selected in order to cover different latitudes and longitudes (specially those latitudes close to the magnetic equator). It has also been checked that these stations provide data with a low number of interruptions.

Figure 13: Example of bubble detected over Galapagos Island on the 19 February 2023.

The Solar Wind driven autoregression model for Ionospheric short-term Forecast (SWIF)

The Solar Wind driven autoregression model for Ionospheric short-term Forecast (SWIF) calculates ionospheric forecasts up to several hours ahead, for the European region. SWIF combines historical and real-time ionospheric observations with solar wind parameters obtained in real time at the L1 point. This is achieved through the cooperation of an autoregression forecasting algorithm, called Time Series AutoRegressive (TSAR), with the empirical Storm Time Ionospheric Model (STIM) that formulates the ionospheric storm time response based on solar wind input (Tzagouri, Koutroumbas and Belehaki, 2009). The STIM's alert detection algorithm is designed to identify storm conditions at L1 point by applying the following quantitative criteria to the magnitude of the IMF, its rate of change and the IMF-Bz component: i) increase in the IMF total magnitude (Bmag): time derivative values greater than 3.8 nT/h or absolute values greater than 13 nT, and ii) southward turning of the IMF-Bz component either simultaneously or few hours later than Bmag increase, with Bz < -10 nT for at least 3 h. The model estimates also the time delay between the storm signatures at L1 point and the ionospheric storm onset taking into account the latitude of the observation point and its local time at L1 storm onset: the time delay for negative storm effects ranges from about 3 to 13 h, while for positive storm effects is about 2–3 h. Finally, STIM formulates the ionospheric storm time response through empirical expressions that provide a correction factor to the reference variation based again on the latitude of the observation point and its local time at the storm onset at L1 point.

plotter		^
GET	/plotter/swif Get SWIF Plot for specified station/interval	v
GET	/plotter/magdata Get MagData [DSCVR] Plot for specified interval	v
swifdb		^
GET	/swifdb/stations List distinct Active STIM Stations	v
GET	/swifdb/tsar/covstats TSAR Temporal Coverage per Station Statistics	v
GET	/swifdb/tsar/rangestats TSAR Temporal Range per Station Statistics	v
GET	/swifdb/forecasts List Forecasts Metadata	v
GET	/swifdb/forecasts/pager List Forecasts Metadata [Pager]	v
GET	/swifdb/forecasts_df Forecasts as Dataframe	v
POST	/swifdb/forecasts_sync_df Forecasts as Dataframe (complex sync request: <ForecastsCov>sync)	v
GET	/swifdb/solardb/magdata List DSCOVR Magdata Metadata	v
GET	/swifdb/solardb/magdata/pager List DSCOVR Magdata Metadata [Pager]	v
GET	/swifdb/solardb/magdata_df DSCOVR Magdata as Dataframe	v
GET	/swifdb/stim/storms Query Interplanetary Storms Detected	v
GET	/swifdb/stim/storm/{pubid} Query Interplanetary Storm by UUID	v
GET	/swifdb/stim/istorms Query Local Storms Detected	v
GET	/swifdb/stim/istorm/{pubid} Query Local Storm by UUID	v
GET	/swifdb/tsar/stormstats TSAR Temporal Range per Station Statistics	v

Figure 14: Interacting with SWIF model through its API - available actions

Parameters
Cancel

Name	Description
start string(datetime) <small>(query)</small>	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text" value="2023-01-04T02:00:00"/>
end string(datetime) <small>(query)</small>	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text" value="2023-01-05T13:59:59"/>
station string <small>(query)</small>	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text" value="AT138"/>

Execute
Clear

Figure 15: Specifying parameters of a plot in SWIF model

Figure 16: Example of result of the SWIF model. The plot provides the forecasted values of the foF2 characteristic, and the observed values for comparison. The grey shaded area corresponds to the time when alert conditions occurred based on the interplanetary magnetic field disturbances. The pink shaded area corresponds to the time when the STIM predictions are effective.

5. Data quality

Advanced model developments rely on the availability of quality-controlled data to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the outcomes. Within the context of PITHIA-NRF, one crucial yet underdiscussed area involves establishing standards for data quality control and management among the participating RI facilities. To address this gap, our focus delves into delineating higher-level data products, in alignment with the guidelines proposed by esteemed organisations such as the Research Data Alliance, ESFRI, and EOSC. This entails an extensive review of domain-specific methodologies, along with the examination of current practices in PITHIA-NRF facility RIs concerning quality control tools and curation processes. Our primary objective is to construct a reference framework that outlines key aspects of data quality, offering guidelines for PITHIA-NRF data providers in assessing and publishing research data. A notable contribution from our initiative is the establishment of a Data Quality Flag, signifying the scientific quality of research data. This effort proves challenging, not only for PITHIA-NRF but also for many other European Research Infrastructures.

PITHIA-NRF facility nodes generate clean data from the raw data collections and utilise standardised processes for higher-level data products. All datasets that will be registered in the e-Science Centre need to be verified for their quality. Each data provider will be responsible for the quality assurance of the datasets.

The quality of digital research data is determined by:

- Their intrinsic scientific quality;
- The quality of metadata that describe the research data;
- The quality of data resources.

Although the data providers are responsible for assessing the quality of their own datasets, the eSC provides recommendations on how to assess the quality. These are summarised in the sections below.

5.1 Scientific Data quality

Scientific quality is defined using the data quality flag (DQF). It describes measures taken to *clean* and *validate* the data, as well as characterise the residual data noise. It is distinct from another data qualifier used in the specification of the Acquisition and Computation metadata documents called the *Data Level*, that characterises the amount of data processing applied to the measurements to obtain higher level data products (in terms of the observed properties). Based on this qualifier the user may extract conclusions regarding data quality. Commonly, Data Level 1 refers to observed properties of the instrument probing signal while Data Level 2 corresponds to the derived geophysical properties of the Feature of Interest, etc. Table 3 provides a list of DQF definitions.

Table 3. Definitions of Data Quality Flags.

DQF	Name	Description
0	RAW	Raw output of Acquisition or model Calculation with no regard to its quality
1	CLEAN	Automatic data conditioning is applied
2	EVALUATED	Provided with confidence and uncertainty metrics
3	VERIFIED-CLEAN	Post-processed manually to ensure removal of data noise
4	VALIDATED	Validated against independent measurements or models

DQF gradations are not mutually exclusive; Data Collection, Acquisition, Computation, and Catalog Subset documents may assign multiple data quality flags for the same data product. For example,

- Volcano Eruption Catalogue: a Subset of the ionogram-derived measurements is registered in the Catalogue that was VERIFIED-CLEAN by manual editing of ionograms and VALIDATED against other measurements of the same study.
- Space Weather Monitoring: assimilative data models that assess the quality of their input data may require data products that are CLEAN and EVALUATED in order to use them in a Kalman-filter assimilation procedure.
- Manually Edited Ionograms: although manual editing ensures that ionogram scaling is correct (VERIFIED-CLEAN), the profile inversion Computation may use an ensemble of software algorithms to evaluate the uncertainty of true height values (EVALUATED).

5.2 Quality of Metadata

Descriptive metadata (DM) describe resources and services with the help of useful key-value pairs and in so far classify them according to a number of specified semantic dimensions. DM also adds information that is not part of the resource or service such as documenting its creation and modification contexts, its internal encoding and formatting principles, its availability and accessibility etc. DM should also include provenance information to allow people to trace back with help of which automatic operations the resource was created.

Where metadata are used in dynamically changing research environments, flexibility is one of the most important requirements: (1) New elements are defined and need to be added; (2) researchers are using different selections of the defined elements to prevent overhead and (3) researchers want to borrow elements from different sets to re-use already existing definitions.

High quality metadata are needed for long-term preservation of observation data generated by the PITHIA-NRF facilities. Based on e-IRG ESFRI Quality Data Management recommendations, a reference check-list is provided below that can be used by PITHIA-NRF data providers to examine the metadata quality:

MQ1: Usage. There is a distinction between descriptive, structural and administrative metadata. These must be provided in accordance with the applicable guidelines of the data repository.

- Descriptive metadata are data required to be able to find research data and that add transparency to their meaning (definition and value) and importance. Examples of descriptive metadata are the data elements of the Dublin Core Element Set⁴, with fields such as Creator, Type, and Date.
- Structural metadata indicate how different components of a set of associated data relate to one another. These metadata are needed to be able to process the research data. When data are coded, the codebook will be a component of the structural metadata.
- Administrative metadata are required to enable permanent access to the research data. This concerns the description of intellectual property, terms of use and access, and so-called preservation metadata needed for sustainable archiving of the research data.

MQ2: Scope. PITHIA-NRF data providers should agree on a set of semantically specific enough elements to describe their data, models and other services and resources. The creation of the PITHIA ontology is an important contribution to this aspect.

MQ3: Provenance. DM should include or refer to provenance information to support long-term preservation and further processing.

⁴ <https://www.dublincore.org/>

MQ4: Persistence. Metadata descriptions need to be persistent, to be identified by persistent identifiers and also to refer to the resources and services they represent by using persistent identifiers.

MQ5: Aggregations. Descriptive metadata have an enormous potential to describe various forms of groupings and can give them an identity, i.e. making them citable.

MQ6: Standardisation. Descriptive metadata needs to be based on well-defined element semantics and a schema-based format to cater for presentations for humans and machine operations. Where fixed schema solutions are given up, elements need to be re-used which are registered in open registries.

MQ7: Interoperability. Descriptive metadata needs to be open and offered for harvesting via widely accepted mechanisms to cater for interdisciplinary usage.

MQ8: Quality. Researchers need to be urged to produce high quality metadata descriptions.

MQ9: Earliness. Researchers should be motivated to create metadata immediately and tool developers should add those descriptors that can be created automatically.

MQ10: Availability. It is a MUST for all resource and service providers to create and provide quality metadata descriptions.

5.3 Quality of Data Resources

Quality of data resources concerns quality of data generation, quality of data repository and quality of data usage.

Quality of Data Generation: When generating research data, PITHIA-NRF data providers should examine the data format and documentation.

DGQ1. Data format. The bits that form a digital research object are organised according to the rules for a particular data format. Preferred formats are formats designated by a data repository for which it guarantees that they can be converted into data formats that will remain readable and usable. The preferred formats should be *de facto* standards employed by PITHIA-NRF communities.

DGQ2. Documentation. Providing metadata describing any kind of research resources (data, models, services) is an urgent requirement for PITHIA-NRF data providers. RDA Recommendation⁵ provides guidelines for documenting data by describing the why, who, what, when, where, and how of the data.

Quality of Data Repository: The data repository is responsible for access and preservation of digital research data on the long term. PITHIA-NRF data providers should consider two factors that determine the quality of the data repository:

DRQ1. Organisation and processes. Organisations that play a role in digital archiving and are establishing a Trusted Digital Repository (TDR) minimally possess

⁵ https://dataoneorg.github.io/Education/bp_step/describe/

a sound financial, organisational and legal basis on the long term. Depending on the task assigned to an organisation, a TDR may distinguish itself qualitatively by carrying out research and by cooperating with other organisations in the realm of data archiving and data infrastructure. The outcomes of such research are shared, both nationally and internationally. In addition, these organisations will also share physical infrastructures, software and other knowledge among each other, where possible.

DRQ2. Technical Infrastructure. The technical infrastructure constitutes the foundation of a Trusted Digital Repository. The OAIS reference model⁶, an ISO standard, is the de facto standard for using digital archiving terminology and defining the functions that a data repository fulfils⁷.

Quality of Data Usage: The quality of the use of research data is determined by the degree to which the data can be used without limitation for scientific research by the various target groups, while complying with certain rules of conduct. The open and free use of research data takes place within the legal frameworks and the policy guidelines as determined by the relevant (national) authorities.

6. Data management policies

PITHIA-NRF developments are based on the adoption of the following common data management policies:

PRI 1. Support European Commission Open Research data policies, and endeavour on bringing the PITHIA-NRF community to a higher level of Openness and FAIRness.

PRI 2. Adopt EOSC relevant standards, incl. AAI, PID and data management etc.

PRI 3. Respect PITHIA-NRF data providers' own development objectives and status, and define policies based on community's requirements.

PRI 4. Ensure consensus through open discussions at each stage of the policy development.

Compliance to open access and FAIR principles is the central policy in PITHIA-NRF data management. Below we provide the main considerations required to align with this policy.

6.1 Open Data

The e-Science Centre functionalities allow the PITHIA-NRF facility nodes to register their metadata and make them publicly accessible. In this sense the access to the functionalities presented in Figure 4 is open. However, PITHIA-NRF policies need to balance openness and protection of scientific information, commercialisation and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR),

⁶ <http://www.oais.info/>

⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Open_Archival_Information_System

privacy concerns, security as well as data management and preservation questions. This is in accordance to the EC approach described as "as open as possible, as closed as necessary". PITHIA-NRF facility nodes are free to specify embargo periods for their data. If data cannot be open, registration of the metadata about the data is encouraged. This will help increase findability and discoverability. It can also include the descriptions of what users have to do to request access.

6.2 FAIR data

FAIR principles were originally defined in 'The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and Stewardship', by Mark Wilkinson et. al., Nature, Scientific Data 3 (2016).

A significant work towards systematically assessing and evaluating of FAIRness levels was delivered by the RDA Working Group in Jun 2020, which created a "FAIR data maturity model"⁸. The model aims to develop a common set of core assessment criteria for FAIRness, specifies indicators for assessing adherence to the FAIR principles, and provides guidelines to assist evaluations. It is adopted by EOSC projects and working forces, e.g., EGI-ACE⁹, EOSC Synergy, EOSC Fair and quality working group, etc.

Based on the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model paper⁹ and the reference template¹⁰, the PITHIA-NRF FAIR Assessment and Evaluation was conducted at the beginning of the project among each PITHIA partner to assess the level of FAIRness of the Data Collections foreseen to be included in the e-Science Centre.

For this purpose, the full list of the FAIR data maturity model indicators was considered (shown in Table 4). **Indicators** are the formulation of measurable aspects of the FAIR principle. In total, 7 Findable, 12 Accessible, 12 Interoperable, and 16 Reusable indicators are specified.

Priorities are based on the understanding that some of the indicators are more important than others. There are three levels:

- **Essential (20)**: utmost importance to achieve FAIRness under most circumstances
- **Important (14)**: might not be of the utmost importance, but substantially increase FAIRness
- **Useful (7)**: nice-to-have but not necessarily indispensable

Table 4. The full list of FAIR data maturity model indicators

Id	Indicators for Findable	Priority
RDA-F1-01M	Metadata identified by a persistent identifier	Essential
RDA-F1-01D	Data identified by a persistent identifier	Essential
RDA-F1-02M	Metadata is identified by a globally unique identifier	Essential
RDA-F1-02D	Data is identified by a globally unique identifier	Essential
RDA-F2-01M	Rich metadata is provided to allow discovery	Essential
RDA-F3-01M	Metadata includes the identifier for the data	Essential

⁸ <https://zenodo.org/record/3909563#.YupwB-xBzj0>

⁹ <https://zenodo.org/records/7463329>

¹⁰ https://zenodo.org/record/3909563/files/FAIR_evaluation_levels_v0.01.xlsx?download=1

RDA-F4-01M	Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed	Essential
Id	Indicators for Accessible	Priority
RDA-A1-01M	Metadata contains information to enable the user to get access to the data	Important
RDA-A1-02M	Metadata can be accessed manually (i.e. with human intervention)	Essential
RDA-A1-02D	Data can be accessed manually (i.e. with human intervention)	Essential
RDA-A1-03M	Metadata identifier resolves to a metadata record	Essential
RDA-A1-03D	Data identifier resolves to a digital object	Essential
RDA-A1-04M	Metadata is accessed through standardised protocol	Essential
RDA-A1-04D	Data is accessible through standardised protocol	Essential
RDA-A1-05D	Data can be accessed automatically (i.e. by a computer program)	Important
RDA-A1.1-01M	Metadata is accessible through a free access protocol	Essential
RDA-A1.1-01D	Data is accessible through a free access protocol	Important
RDA-A1.2-01D	Data is accessible through an access protocol that supports authentication and authorisation	Useful
RDA-A2-01M	Metadata is guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available	Essential
Id	Indicators for Interoperable	Priority
RDA-I1-01M	Metadata uses knowledge representation expressed in standardised format	Important
RDA-I1-01D	Data uses knowledge representation expressed in standardised format	Important
RDA-I1-02M	Metadata uses machine-understandable knowledge representation	Important
RDA-I1-02D	Data uses machine-understandable knowledge representation	Important
RDA-I2-01M	Metadata uses FAIR-compliant vocabularies	Important
RDA-I2-01D	Data uses FAIR-compliant vocabularies	Useful
RDA-I3-01M	Metadata includes references to other metadata	Important
RDA-I3-01D	Data includes references to other data	Useful
RDA-I3-02M	Metadata includes references to other data	Useful
RDA-I3-02D	Data includes qualified references to other data	Useful
RDA-I3-03M	Metadata includes qualified references to other metadata	Important
RDA-I3-04M	Metadata includes qualified references to other data	Useful
Id	Indicators for Reusable	Priority
RDA-R1-01M	Plurality of accurate and relevant attributes are provided to allow reuse	Essential
RDA-R1.1-01M	Metadata includes information about the licence under which the data can be reused	Essential
RDA-R1.1-02M	Metadata refers to a standard reuse licence	Important
RDA-R1.1-03M	Metadata refers to a machine-understandable reuse licence	Important
RDA-R1.2-01M	Metadata includes provenance information according to community-specific standards	Important
RDA-R1.2-02M	Metadata includes provenance information according to a cross-community language	Useful
RDA-R1.3-01M	Metadata complies with a community standard	Essential
RDA-R1.3-01D	Data complies with a community standard	Essential

RDA-R1.3-02M	Metadata is expressed in compliance with a machine-understandable community standard	Essential
RDA-R1.3-02D	Data is expressed in compliance with a machine-understandable community standard	Important

The result from this assessment is that the majority of the nodes have to implement additional development in order to be fully compliant with the FAIR principles, considering that a major effort in PITHIA-NRF is to bring the nodes to achieve FAIRness. In this assessment, the gaps were analysed and required actions were examined, including specific tasks per node to make data collections compatible with the e-Science Centre registration requirements and with the PITHIA Ontology. In addition, mappings are provided between the design and implementation of e-Science Centre, PITHIA Ontology etc. against FAIR indicators. PITHIA-NRF nodes are also involved in discussing how to implement the recommended policies. The results show that by implementing the e-Science Centre, and by registering all data collections via API, the FAIRness will be drastically improved. Towards the end of the project (early 2025), the nodes will be evaluated again regarding the FAIRness.

7. Conclusion and outlook

PITHIA-NRF "Plasmasphere Ionosphere Thermosphere Integrated Research Environment and Access services: a Network of Research Facilities" is a European Commission (EC) Research Infrastructure funded by the Horizon 2020 Programme which runs from 2021 to 2025. PITHIA-NRF aims at building a European distributed network that integrates observing facilities, data processing tools and prediction models dedicated to ionosphere, thermosphere and plasmasphere research. For the first time, PITHIA-NRF integrates, on a European scale, key national and regional research infrastructures such as EISCAT, LOFAR, Ionosondes and Digisondes, GNSS receivers, Doppler sounding systems, riometers, and VLF receivers. The integration ensures optimal use and joint development. PITHIA-NRF is designed to provide organised access to experimental facilities, FAIR data, standardised data products, training and innovation services. PITHIA-NRF promotes research advances in the field of upper atmosphere and near-Earth space, through the integration of data collections from satellite missions and results from key prediction models that can be accessed by scientific users for joint exploitation with the data collected from the research infrastructures of the network. PITHIA-NRF paves the way for new observing technologies, and for the standardisation of software and high-level data products tuned to meet the requirements of technologies concerned, linking best-in-class R&D facilities to provide seamless multi-technology services.

By the end of the EC funded period (in 2025), PITHIA-NRF is expected to deliver a unique European Infrastructure that produces services to the international community of upper atmosphere researchers and stakeholders, including early-career researchers and software and instrument development professionals. The following main services are deployed:

- Standardisation of data registration, discovery and access, based on the domain-specific ontology and standard-based metadata

- Standardisation of scientific models' registration, and delivery of data products for research, development and innovation
- Standardisation of policies for the optimised operation of experimental facilities
- Subsidised trans-national access to research facilities for academics and SMEs ensuring a continuous cooperation and interaction with data providers and scientists
- E-Science tools to support R&D projects, while ensuring compliance with FAIR criteria
- Innovative solutions for software development, high-level data product definition and the development and deployment of new experimental facilities

The development of these services is supported by the TransNational Access (TNA) programme, which is conducted in the framework of open calls for projects, and by the Innovation Framework which organises discussions with expert stakeholders on their needs and experience from using the PITHIA-NRF services. The combined effect of all these activities should provide the possibility for PITHIA-NRF to:

- Become an internationally-renowned infrastructure for Research and Development leading to excellent research advances in the upper atmosphere and near-Earth space domains;
- Provide simple and open access to data fully compatible to the FAIR principles and to advanced multidisciplinary services;
- Develop novel business practices, project management services and new technologies that together accelerate end-to-end software standardisation and instrument development and calibration.

PITHIA-NRF has the potential for enormous impact on structuring the scientific community, producing innovation, providing societal benefits and influencing future governance and funding decisions. However, the main achievement that drives all impacts is the expected scientific advances. The major advantage of an integrated research environment is the sharing of data, services, facilities and equipment with all stakeholders, thereby avoiding unnecessary duplication of effort. Using this background knowledge and the support of PITHIA-NRF experts, excellent and innovative scientific results are expected to emerge from users and especially from the young generation of researchers and engineers. An important expected benefit for the operations domain is the release of validated data products with improved accuracy that could serve the requirements of the Space Safety and Security Programme of the European Space Agency and of the European Union Space Programme.

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